

**AIHE Academic Institute for Higher Education GmbH
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MSc Clinical Psychology

**Is this pain yours? A literature review on transmission of historical
intergenerational trauma and resilience**

Master's Dissertation

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Abstract

This literature review addresses how historical trauma is transmitted intergenerationally, focusing on attachment styles and parenting approaches, family communication, as well as resilience in the communities affected by Soviet and Nazi committed genocides. Millions of people have been harmed by these regimes directly, and their impact may extend to the second and the third generations. Having conducted a literature search, 23 studies were selected for the review. Integrative methods were used to analyse the studies, while thematic analysis was used to find patterns across the studies. Family communication emerged as one of the most common trauma transmission pathways: open communication was associated with transmission of resilience, while absent communication was associated with transmission of traumatic symptoms. Also, trauma tended to be transmitted through insecure attachment styles, and overprotective or avoidant parenting approaches. The results were comparable across samples, though communities affected by Soviet genocides reported more mistrust and helplessness, which could be explained by the historical context of the Soviet crimes. Finally, the findings on intergenerationally transmitted resilience imply that the survivors of these regimes and their offspring have unique strengths that go beyond the trauma-induced vulnerabilities, therefore, future research on intergenerational resilience could benefit the field.

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List of Abbreviations

C-PTSD	Complex Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder
ICD-11	International Classification of Diseases, the 11th edition
PTG	Post-Traumatic Growth
PTSD	Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder

1. Introduction

The twentieth century was marked by oppressive regimes and genocides (Snyder, 2010). As the offspring of survivors grow up, they start exploring their historical trauma legacy. Historical trauma can be defined as systematic intentional violence from the outsiders affecting entire communities, causing long-term distress and a loss of community members (Evans-Campbell, 2008; Sotero, 2006). This traumatic experience can be transmitted from survivors to their offspring, affecting the development of the community, its health, well-being and prosperity (Gailienė, 2019; Sotero, 2006). Intergenerational trauma outlines how second, third and the following generations experience traumatic symptoms, even though they have never been directly exposed to traumatic events (Mažulytė-Rašytienė, 2017).

Intergenerational trauma can be transmitted in different ways. Firstly, there are biological transmission paths, such as epigenetic transmission, where trauma-related biochemical changes that alter gene expression get passed to the next generation (Kellermann, 2013). On a psychological level, trauma may be transmitted through family interactions, such as parent-child attachment styles, parenting types and family communication (Salberg, 2015). However, there is emerging research showing that transmission entails not only the negative traumatic consequences but also positive adaptation – resilience (Shmotkin et al., 2011). In some research, resilience is defined as coping skills, such as a sense of strength, that can be transmitted alongside vulnerabilities (Hu et al., 2015). Resilience can also be related to Post-Traumatic Growth, the – seemingly unlikely – positive developments in one's outlook and life after a traumatic experience. Another definition depicts resilience as protective factors that may prevent the trauma transmission altogether (Sagi-Schwartz et al., 2008).

While the significance of and the research body on Nazi-committed genocide is well-established, less data exists on the crimes committed by the Soviet Union, even though it may have had a comparable victim toll (Naimark, 2010; Rummel, 1994). About 6 million Jewish people and 6 million more ethnic, sexual, and other groups died due to Nazi committed genocide (United States Holocaust Memorial Museum, 2023). Under the Soviet regime, if we only include the deaths related to Soviet imprisonment or deportation, the death toll is estimated to be from 3 million to 3.5 million (Ellman, 2002). Holodomor – a man-made famine in Ukraine – is estimated to have from 5 to 10 million deaths (Stark, 2010). Some estimates, including deportations, targeted killings and Holodomor, suggest that over 61 million people died due to the Soviet regime (Rummel, 1994).

These forms of oppression, their duration, scale, and impact qualify as historical trauma (Mažulytė-Rašytienė, 2017). According to Raphael Lemkin, who coined the term

genocide, this term concerns not only mass murder of individuals, but the aim to destroy the culture and nation itself (Lemkin & Irvin-Erickson, 2014). Soviet actions such as killings, as well as deportations and imprisonments leading to deaths, can be defined as genocidal actions as they were directly related to the policies aiming to limit and eradicate local languages, religions and cultural rituals (Lemkin & Irvin-Erickson, 2014; Schmaltz & Sinner, 2002). Soviet oppression against the Baltic countries, Georgians, Ukrainians and other occupied nations can be recognised as a genocide, according to 1948 Genocide Convention (Sagatiené, 2021; Pohl, 2000; Yakubovskiy, 2021). Even in the case of persecuting people within Russia, Soviet policies of ethnic cleansing targeting Crimean Tatars and other ethnic groups, can be defined as genocide (Özçelik, 2020). According to Shaw (2017), the Soviet Union was influential in affecting the definition of genocide agreed upon in the convention by successfully arguing to exclude the elimination of political groups from the concept of genocide. While there is a debate around the definition of genocide in the context of Soviet crimes, some academics call for an even more inclusive definition, especially when it comes to political persecution (Mälksoo, 2001; Naimark, 2010). It is important to emphasise that the Soviet regime lasted up until 1991, and therefore the research on its crimes, or even the accessibility of their documentation, are still limited (Naimark, 2010).

Therefore, one of the goals of this review is to understand the limited research available and to encourage future research in the area. Beyond the academic interest, this data is needed to acknowledge the impact of the genocidal regimes, bringing justice and closure to the victims (Danieli, 2009). As the victims' offspring are learning more about their traumatic past, clinical psychologists need information and tools to understand the challenges of their clients, especially since historical intergenerational trauma is not well-established in the 11th edition of International Classification of Diseases (ICD-11). Sometimes historical trauma can be associated with and measured as PTSD (Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder) or Complex Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (C-PTSD) (Ehlers et al., 2022; Mutuyimana & Maercker, 2023). PTSD is characterised by avoidance of the traumatic event memories, re-experiencing such memories, hypervigilance, anxiety, shame, sadness. C-PTSD occurs in the contexts of repeated, prolonged traumatic events, and while it contains most of the PTSD symptoms, it also includes disruptions in affect regulation, difficulty sustaining relationships and feeling close to others, lowered self-worth (World Health Organisation, 2022). Coincidentally, similar experiences are reported by second and third generations of genocide survivors (Adelman, 1995; Aintablian et al., 2018; Mazor & Tal, 1996).

There are a number of factors why the literature on Soviet genocide is scarce. Firstly, the victims of the Soviet regime were prohibited from reporting on its crimes and their

impact. Secondly, Soviets focused on damaging the reputation of psychology and psychiatry as a field (Kazlauskas & Želvienė, 2016). Thirdly, after regaining independence from the Soviet Union, many countries lacked resources for conducting such research (Kazlauskas et al., 2017). These factors may have had implications on the traumatic experiences as well. Since Soviet regime lasted longer than the ones committed by Nazi regime, the victims and their offspring were denied the opportunity to process the traumatic experiences or even acknowledge their existence (Etkind, 2009). Therefore, this review will aim to address the existing literature on historical intergenerational trauma transmission in the communities affected by Soviet genocidal actions, while using Nazi genocide literature for comparative context.

2. Research Questions

Based on the research aims, the following research questions were formulated. Firstly, how does intergenerational historical trauma get transmitted through attachment styles and other parenting approaches in families who have experienced Nazi or Soviet genocide? Secondly, how does intergenerational historical trauma get transmitted through family communication in families who have experienced Nazi or Soviet genocide? Thirdly, how is resilience transmitted in families who have experienced Nazi or Soviet genocide? Finally, how does the intergenerational trauma transmission differ between the offspring of victims from Nazi and Soviet genocide?

3. Theoretical Background

3.1 Attachment Theory

According to Bowlby (1969), attachments are bonds that are formed between children and their caregivers, affecting children's development of a sense of safety and self-worth. The types of attachment are divided primarily into secure and insecure ones. When children have a secure attachment to their caregivers, they feel free to explore their surroundings, knowing the caregivers are available to comfort them – while they may get worried when the caregiver leaves, they are easily soothed when the caregiver comes back. When children have insecure attachment, it can be defined either as anxious attachment, characterised by clingy, fearful behaviour, or avoidant attachment, that is characterised by emotional distancing (Ainsworth, 1979). Disorganised attachment may switch from anxious to avoidant attachment types and is often a sign of traumatic history (Cook et al., 2005; Main & Solomon, 1986).

Attachment styles are found to be transmitted from parents to their offspring, and together with them, traumatic experiences can be passed intergenerationally as well (Aloni

et al., 2020; Iyengar et al., 2014; Gravener et al., 2012). In addition, attachment styles can be seen as the path through which the trauma gets transmitted (Salberg, 2015). Complex trauma is related to damaging the sense of safety, therefore, it can affect the formation of secure attachment (Cook et al., 2005). According to Van der Kolk et al. (1996), secure attachment works as a protective mechanism against the expression of trauma.

3.2 Family Systems Theory

Family Systems theory envisions the family unit as a system, where family members affect one another, relying on each other, and trying to protect each other in times of need (Figley, 1988). When there is trauma history present in the family, it may lead to disruptive outcomes, such as parent-child role reversal known as parentification, as well as disturbed differentiation of self, affecting the balance between one's sense of individuality and a sense of connectedness (Calatrava et al., 2022; Hooper, 2007). In addition, since family members seek to maintain a sense of harmony, communication about emotionally difficult matters may be avoided – which may lead to a lack of discussion about family's traumatic past (Crittenden & Dallos, 2009).

Research shows that differentiation of self, and other dynamics within family systems, can be transmitted intergenerationally (Abrams, 1999; Čepukienė & Neophytou, 2024). Differentiation of self can be seen as a protective factor related to resilience (Süloğlu & Güler, 2021). In addition, according to Bowen (1978), people maintaining their family relationships and values show higher resilience in managing stress in their lives.

3.3 Post-Traumatic Growth

Post-Traumatic Growth (PTG) can be defined as positive shifts related to one's personality, functioning or cognition after a traumatic experience (Ortega-Williams et al., 2021). The authors created a historical trauma-PTG framework, suggesting that personal growth is interconnected with communal growth.

According to Berger and Weiss (2009), PTG can be applied to Family Systems theory, resulting in positive outcomes for the whole family unit, such as improved relationships, strengthened family identity, better focus on priorities, more life appreciation. Therefore, PTG may help to explain how families that experienced historical trauma can recover and even experience growth together.

Interestingly, while PTG may be used synonymously with resilience in some research, their differences are debated (Westphal & Bonanno, 2007). The difference may lie in the different definitions of resilience, as the authors argue that people showing more resilience would not necessarily display signs of PTG, because resilience implies a lack of

traumatic symptoms, a lack of issues, and therefore, a lack of a need to work those issues out – meaning, a lack of potential for post-traumatic growth. For example, Levine et al. (2009) found that higher resilience was associated with lower PTG.

4. Method

4.1 Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Four inclusion criteria were used. Firstly, the empirical studies containing both qualitative and quantitative methods were included. Secondly, studies of second and/or third generations were included, the first generation defined as the direct victims of genocide. Thirdly, the samples containing offspring of people who survived Soviet or Nazi committed genocides were included. Finally, studies that were published in or translated to English were included. One non-English (Lithuanian) paper was nonetheless included due to the author's native proficiency in the language.

Four exclusion criteria were used. Firstly, reviews, meta-analyses and opinion pieces were excluded. Secondly, studies where all generations in the sample were exposed to the genocide were excluded as they would not be demonstrating transmission that this review is focused on. Thirdly, studies were excluded when they did not address historical trauma or psychological transmission: studies focused on personal trauma, on biological transmission of trauma, studies detailing only the consequences of trauma without addressing the ways of transmission or resilience factors were excluded. Finally, duplicate data samples were excluded: two cases were found where studies released in different years relied on the same data, collected at the same time, from the same individuals. The duplicate studies were excluded to maintain the accuracy of the results, and the scientific integrity of the review.

The criteria can be justified through a few key factors. Firstly, since the data on this topic is so limited, especially in the sample on Soviet regime, it was important to maximise the type of studies that could be analysed. Therefore, both quantitative and qualitative studies were included, both second and third generation studies were included, and no date-based exclusion criteria was created. Secondly, it was important to maximise the comparability of the studies, making sure that they can answer the research questions. Therefore, the studies where the offspring were directly affected by the genocidal actions were excluded, other types of traumas were excluded, duplicate data sets were excluded, while only the selected samples of Nazi and Soviet genocides were included.

4.2 Search

The search was conducted on the 11th of October 2024 on PsycNet, DOAJ and PubMed databases. PRISMA statement was used to guide the search process of this integrative review (Page et al., 2021).

The following keywords were used: ‘intergenerational trauma’ or ‘transgenerational trauma’, ‘Soviet’ or ‘Holocaust’. Initially, Boolean logic was tested, however, the results returned were not as relevant to the research questions as using the sets of keywords separately. In addition, after testing the initial search string, few results were retrieved. Therefore, the approach was adapted and only the essential keywords were left, because using more keywords, including some of the key variables as “attachment” or “resilience”, produced insufficient results and left out a considerable number of studies that analysed the variables addressing the research questions.

Using the keywords ‘soviet intergenerational trauma’, 15 results were found, out of which 13 did not answer the research questions. From the remaining two, one was inaccessible due to (Russian) language, and one was a review. All 15 results were excluded, however, after analysing the references used in the review paper, three relevant papers were selected from the references. No duplicates were found across the databases. The alternative keyword string ‘soviet transgenerational trauma’ did not yield any results on PsycNet and DOAJ, while producing the same number of results on PubMed (12) with one study being different, which was excluded due to being irrelevant to the research questions.

Using the keywords ‘holocaust intergenerational trauma’, 161 results were found, out of which 18 were duplicates and 104 did not answer the research questions. From the remaining 39 studies, 24 were reviews or non-empirical studies. From the 15 relevant studies left, one was inaccessible. Finally, 14 remaining studies were selected to be used for analysis. The alternative variation including a keyword ‘transgenerational’ yielded 116 results, out of which 31 studies were new, having removed the duplicates. Out of them, 21 did not answer the research questions and six were reviews or non-empirical papers. From the four relevant studies left, three were inaccessible. In the end, one study was selected.

Having read the selected studies, five more studies were added from references. This resulted in the final number of 23 studies. Eight of them concerning Soviet genocide, and 16 on Nazi genocide – one comparative study focused on both samples, as can be seen in Figure 1.

After analysing the abstracts of inaccessible papers – the versions of which were either not found online or were not in English – it was concluded that the general findings of them tended to be broadly consistent with the trends of the selected papers. The authors of inaccessible papers have been contacted when their email addresses were available online.

Figure 1.
The Flow Chart of the Search Process

Note. This figure represents the literature search process across the scientific databases. While the Boolean logic was initially tested, it did not produce relevant and sufficient results, therefore, separate searches for different samples and synonyms were run, producing a high number of duplicates. Studies that did not answer the research questions or that met the exclusion criteria otherwise (e.g. review studies and meta-analyses) were excluded, with overall eight studies added from the references of the papers that were found. The final count included 23 studies, with one of the studies addressing both Soviet and Nazi regime samples.

4.3 Sample

Out of the eight studies related to Soviet genocide, three were quantitative studies, four were qualitative studies, and one contained both qualitative and quantitative elements. Considerable effort was invested into finding peer-reviewed studies, and due to the limited research available on the topic, two dissertations and two chapters containing original research were included in the final sample. The rest of the studies were peer-reviewed. Out of 16 studies on Nazi genocide, six were quantitative studies, seven were qualitative studies, and three were mixed. All studies were peer-reviewed.

Out of all 23 studies, eight studies focused on trauma transmission to only the second generation, 13 studies reported on trauma transmission to the third generation (out of which nine studies included both the second and the third generation participants), and two studies did not specify the generations, indicating that the results concern second or third generation participants in one study, and the family members of the first generation in another study.

In terms of the cultural and ethnic diversity, out of the eight studies on the Soviet regime, one was conducted in Georgia, four in Lithuania, two in Ukraine, and one in Russia. Five of them focused on killings, deportations and imprisonment throughout the time of the Soviet regime, two of them focused on Holodomor famine and one of them focused specifically on Stalin's Purge of 1937-1939, which is defined as a particularly deadly period of the Soviet history when millions of people were tortured, sent to concentration camps, deported to Siberia and killed (Baker & Gippenreiter, 1994). Out of the 16 studies on the Nazi regime, nine of them were conducted in Israel, three in the United States of America, one in Italy, one in Hungary, one in Brazil, and one in Australia. All the studies on the Nazi genocidal actions in this review focused on the Holocaust, with the participants usually described as the offspring of concentration camp survivors, or, more broadly, as the offspring of people who lived under the Nazi regime and survived.

4.4 Analysis

The selected studies will be presented in an integrative review. To process quantitative, qualitative, and mixed method data from diverse samples, integrative review methodology by Whitemore & Knafl (2005) was used.

The analysis of the studies was conducted relying on thematic analysis by Thomas & Harden (2008). Firstly, codes were assigned to analysed concepts based on the research questions, such as "attachment", "parenting", "resilience", with new codes created as patterns in the studies emerged, such as "mistrust", "sadness", "anxiety". Secondly, descriptive themes were developed based on these codes, such as parenting approaches

(involving parental styles, avoidance, overprotection, parent-child role reversal), family atmosphere (involving sadness, anxiety and other emotion-related codes), resilience patterns (involving patriotism, optimism, well-being, respect towards the parents, pride), traumatic symptoms (involving sadness, anxiety, fear, PTSD symptoms), family communication (open communication, reflective communication, fragmented communication, absent communication, hidden communication, avoided communication). Thirdly, analytical themes were created based on interconnections among the descriptive themes and individual codes, to provide insight into the findings. The Results and Discussion are structured based on the research questions, while utilising thematic analysis to identify the themes, understand and interpret the findings. See Results for the overview of the analytic themes that emerged from the findings.

5. Results

5.1 Attachment Styles and Parenting Approaches

5.1.1 Attachment styles

5.1.1.1 Soviet Regime. Javakhishvili (2018) analysed the attachment styles carried by the offspring of Georgians who were oppressed by the Soviet regime, finding that the relationship pattern, as well as the attachment style, were transmitted from the second generation to the third. In the interviews, the second generation discussed the hyper-protectiveness of their parents, and parentification. The interviews with the third generation revealed that the same pattern of hyper-protectiveness and parentification was found in the parental relationship between the second and the third generations, interfering with the process of achieving autonomy. The author suggested that this pattern shows insecure, ambivalent attachment, that may be explained by trauma-induced anxiety.

Zasiekina et al. (2021) compared the traumatic experiences of Holocaust and Holodomor survivors in Ukraine. Similarly, they found patterns of insecure attachment in both samples, both among the second and the third-generation survivors, discussing it in the context of complex intense emotions – such as fear, anger, disgust – caused by the genocide trauma, transmitted across generations, and interfering with a secure parent-child bond. Therefore, while the focus on the reasons behind insecure attachment was different in these samples – discussing parentification or emotions in the family – these studies are painting a similar picture of extreme emotions affecting attachment styles through parental fearfulness and protectiveness.

5.1.1.2 Nazi Regime. Insecure attachment was found to be transmitted to the second and third generations (Scharf, 2007; Scharf & Mayseless, 2011; Zasiékina et al., 2021). Scharf (2007) found that adolescent grandchildren of Holocaust survivors had higher levels of ambivalent attachment style when both of their parents were from the Holocaust-affected families. In addition, adolescents with both parents from Holocaust-affected families rated their parents as less accepting and less encouraging of autonomy – these perceptions were correlated with adolescents' lower self-perception and higher levels of ambivalent attachment style. There was one finding inconsistent with the rest of the data, reporting that adolescents with a father from Holocaust-affected family showed lower levels of ambivalent attachment style than the adolescents from a group unaffected by Holocaust. However, only 12 participants were in this group, and the authors expressed a need for replication of this result with a higher sample. Signs of insecure attachment were also found among second and third generation offspring of Holocaust survivors (Zasiékina et al., 2021). Scharf and Mayseless (2011) discovered a similar pattern of findings, showing that neglecting the needs for autonomy, as well as competence, results in disorganised attachment for second and third generations.

However, Sagi-Schwartz et al. (2003), did not find evidence for intergenerational trauma transmission through attachment styles. While they confirmed that Holocaust survivors tended to have less secure attachment than the comparison group that has not experienced Holocaust, their offspring did not differ from the comparison group – neither in terms of attachment styles, nor in terms of traumatic stress or maternal behaviour. The authors explained these effects as a presence of resilience.

5.1.2 Parenting Approaches

5.1.2.1 Soviet Regime. Anxiety and fear were common emotions in the families affected by Soviet genocides (Bezo & Maggi, 2015; Javakhishvili, 2018; Zasiékina et al., 2021). In a study of Holodomor survivors and their offspring, the third generation saw their parents as avoidant of contact, anxious, fearful, passive, ashamed, and closed off to others. They defined this state as staying in a constant survival mode (Bezo & Maggi, 2015). Similarly, Javakhishvili (2018) found that the third generation tended to describe their parents as overprotective, authoritarian, and anxious, describing the family atmosphere as filled with fear – fear of the authorities and mistrust of people. Just as in the Holodomor study, the second generation tended to distance themselves from their children, reluctant to talk about their trauma. Fear featured in these family accounts as well, with the second generation reporting fear about the security of their country. These emotions from the family environment were passed to the third generation, as they reported often feeling scared,

obsessive, sad, anxious, ashamed (Baker & Gippenreiter, 1994; Bezo & Maggi, 2015; Zasiiekina et al., 2021).

In contrast, Mažulytė-Rašytienė (2017) discovered that the offspring of the Soviet oppression victims found their mothers to be less overprotective compared to the offspring from families that did not experience direct oppression. In addition, the participants rated their fathers as more caring compared to the non-victim offspring responses. It is worth mentioning that the study was quantitative and focused on resilience, so more nuanced accounts on family atmosphere were not studied.

5.1.2.2 Nazi Regime. A pattern of parent-child role reversal was transmitted across generations (Letzter-Pouw et al, 2014; Scharf & Mayseless, 2011; Wiseman, 2008; Zasiiekina et al., 2021). The second generation described their parents as anxious, overprotective, and failing to meet their needs. The third generation also reported feeling controlled, while showing signs of parentification – for example, they avoided sharing worrying news to protect their mothers. Second generation tended to avoid experiencing their feelings in order not to suffer, and modelled this approach to the third generation, distancing themselves emotionally. The third generation reported emotional numbness (Zasiiekina et al., 2021). Similarly, Wiseman (2008) found that the second generation saw their parents as overprotective, neglecting the emotional needs of their offspring while over-emphasising their physical needs, which facilitated the parent-child role reversal and led to loneliness both in relation to their peers and their parents. Scharf and Mayseless (2011) established that when offspring were not provided with a sense of competence, autonomy and relatedness, they tended to neglect their own needs and attempted to meet parents' needs instead, contributing to the role-reversal pattern. Wiseman et al. (2006) showed that parents' controlling responses were linked to a reaction of anger by the second generation, but parent's angry responses were not linked to the offspring's anger - they were seen as vulnerable reactions, and were linked to a sense of guilt, which was also associated with conflict avoidance. The author suggested that this pattern had contributed to "mutual overprotection", also implying signs of parentification. Letzter-Pouw et al. (2014) suggested that parental burden tended to revert parent-child roles. They observed the transmission of parental burden to the second and third generations, which was linked to more post-traumatic symptoms and Holocaust salience, defined as the lingering thoughts, behaviours and feelings associated with Holocaust. These links were not found in the comparison sample.

Reduced autonomy was linked to anxiety, PTSD and other trauma-related symptoms (Békés & Starrs 2024; Gangi et al., 2009). Gangi et al. (2009) concluded that the families of Holocaust survivors tended to limit autonomy, showing reduced independence and more

submission among the second generation. They worried about relationships and avoided intimate relationships more than the control group, which may be partially explained by the findings of their lower self-worth and higher anxiety than controls. Békés and Starrs (2024) studied parental styles, discussing their impact on mental health symptoms such as PTSD, C-PTSD, anxiety, and depression. They found that the second generation had higher levels of the mental health symptoms when their parents used victim style, while numb style was associated with these symptoms as well, apart from anxiety. Fighter style was not linked to any symptoms neither for second nor for the third generation. Fighter style was the most common, while the victim style was the least common in the studied families. The authors suggested that traumatic transmission was influenced by parenting and parents' coping abilities more than by the generational distance from the traumatic event. The victim style can be associated with overprotectiveness and control, the numb style can be associated with silence and avoidance of communication, while the fighter style may be linked to efforts to maintain identity, making this study consistent with the previous ones showing the link between the traumatised and the overprotective or avoidant parenting. Interestingly, this was the only study that found higher levels of traumatic symptoms in the third generation than in the second generation, the authors suggesting that since control groups were not used, more research is needed, especially controlling for age groups.

5.2 Family Communication

5.2.1 Soviet Regime

Multiple studies found that the traumatic family history was often not discussed within the family, and even when they were, the offspring were told to not talk about it outside of the family (Baker & Gippenreiter, 1994; Bezo & Maggi, 2015; Javakhishvili, 2018; Vaskelienė et al., 2011). The third-generation offspring reported difficulty in complying with this rule, feeling like they had to constantly control themselves, being unable to share their thoughts with their friends or teachers (Baker & Gippenreiter, 1994; Vaskelienė et al., 2011). Most of the offspring only learned about the family history as adults and reported difficulties making sense of it (Javakhishvili, 2018).

In the cases of absent communication, the reasons were both psychological (indicating emotional intensity) and political (avoiding Soviet persecution) (Bezo & Maggi, 2015; Vaskelienė et al., 2011). Some of the emotional reasons were linked to the trauma transmission: the third generation noticed that parents' anxiety led to constant busyness to avoid conversations, which led to a lack of communication (Bezo & Maggi, 2015). The significance of the political reasons is supported by the fact that communication about oppression became more frequent and open after Lithuania declaring independence from

the Soviet Union (Vaskelienė et al., 2011). In addition, the second generation said they learned that they had to be silent out of fear, being aware of the social and political consequences of speaking out (Bezo & Maggi, 2015).

Open communication was often associated with resilience (Javakhishvili, 2018; Mažulytė-Rašytienė, 2017; Vaskelienė et al., 2011). Open communication within the family was linked to a sense of strength and meaning, respect to the oppressed parents, resilience, and pride. However, some open conversations resulted in sadness and anger for the second generation, especially in those cases when the conversations were overly detailed (Vaskelienė et al., 2011). According to Javakhishvili (2018), those third-generation participants who had open discussions about family trauma history in childhood, tended to see more positive outcomes of it, such as heightened empathy, resilience, and patriotism. In addition, more third generation participants saw positive outcomes compared to the second generation. Conversations with the first generation were seen as protective against the traumatic effects, if the oppression stories were framed as meaningful – if they were described as mere misunderstandings, no protective effect of communication was seen. Contrary to the findings of Vaskelienė et al. (2011), even the stories that were seen as too detailed and too emotional seemed to have a positive effect, as they contributed to the processing and ascribing meaning to the trauma. The author indicated two communication types, with Emotional-reflective style facilitating meaning-making and Conspiracy of silence preventing this process (Javakhishvili, 2018). Mažulytė-Rašytienė (2017) demonstrated that the families with trauma history had more conversations about the trauma than the comparison group, which is consistent with the finding that the offspring from the latter group knew less about their family history. Most of the victim families (84.98%) had these family discussions. The type of communication used was significant: families with traumatic history expressed sadness and humour more, as well as more sense of strength and pride. It may indicate that the trauma was being processed and integrated, which may explain the study's finding that the second and third generation offspring had higher scores of well-being and optimism than the comparison group (Mažulytė-Rašytienė, 2017).

Even if no trauma memories are shared in a family, the trauma may be transmitted through a non-verbal approach – a third-generation participant described remembering her grandmother always crying and staying quiet. This finding suggested yet another type of transmission – non-verbal communication (Zasiekina et al., 2021).

Finally, there is silence on the societal level. Zasiekina et al. (2021) indicated that most Ukrainians found it important to remember and commemorate Holodomor, as the Soviet regime tried to hide it, sharing the aim to break the silence and to start communication about the traumatic events on the societal and state level.

5.2.2 Nazi Regime

The communication in the family was found to influence the transmission of both the traumatic effects and resilience (Braga, 2012; Johns et al., 2022; Giladi & Bell, 2012). The communication style affected the second generation's ability to process and integrate the parental trauma: open, loving, humour-filled communication was associated with resilience, and more fragmented, indirect, secretive communication was associated with more pronounced trauma experience in the second generation. The authors explained the findings through fear and avoidance of other negative emotions – parents wanted to protect their offspring from the family trauma, which led to less communication, making it harder for the offspring to process these events (Braga, 2012). Similarly, open verbal communication as well as higher differentiation of self, were linked to lower traumatic stress and higher psychological well-being for both second and third generations. Poorer communication and lower differentiation of self were linked with more traumatic stress. The fact that lower levels of differentiation of self were associated with poorer family communication relates these findings to other studies reporting overprotective, authoritarian parenting being associated with the intergenerational trauma (Giladi & Bell, 2012). Unhealthy communication, defined as indirect and guilt-inducing, was associated with lower mental well-being, such as more anxiety and depression, in the lives of second and third generations of Holocaust survivors. Healthier – more frequent and willing – communication was not found to be associated with better mental well-being, which, authors suggested, may mean that unhealthy communication is more impactful than healthy communication (Johns et al., 2022).

Communication type may be also related to parenting style (Békés & Starss, 2024; Wiseman et al., 2006; Wiseman, 2008). When parents were silent about the experienced trauma, it affected the offspring's ability to express their emotions and needs, leading to a sense of guilt, mutual overprotection, and loneliness (Wiseman et al., 2006). Second generation shared a need for more open communication, stating that their parents struggled to openly talk about traumatic events (Wiseman, 2008). Also, numb parental style was related to a lack of communication about the trauma in the family, suggesting that trauma gets transmitted not (only) through active parenting, but through a lack of communication and emotional expression (Békés & Starss, 2024).

In addition, communication about Holocaust was linked to a sense of identity (Johns et al., 2022; Kassai & Motta, 2006). Affective communication was correlated with ethnic identification, showing the link between more reflective communication within the family and the offspring developing a stronger sense of ethnic identity (Kassai & Motta, 2006). More frequent communication about Holocaust and stronger ethnic identity were linked to more

historical loss awareness – more frequent thinking about Holocaust and the related events (Johns et al., 2022).

According to Cohn and Morrison (2018), a new type of trauma transmission can be observed in the third generation, in contrast to other studies. The third generation was described as active in the search for information about the traumatic family past, outside of family communication. The researchers claimed that this self-research approach is emerging as information about Holocaust is becoming more accessible independently. Having said that, this qualitative study had only 6 participants, and therefore the results may not be generalisable.

Out of all the studies reviewed, only one of them saw the silence between the parent and child as a potentially positive type of communication (Kidron et al, 2019). The authors explained the shared silence as an interaction without words, rather than a lack of communication, and linked it with resilience.

In contrast to other studies, Kassai and Motta (2006) did not find evidence for intergenerational trauma transmission. However, this quantitative study measured transmission through a STROOP test, that may not have captured the traumatic effects – they presented the participants with colours and words on the cards to test if they will react differently to Holocaust-related words. This operationalisation choice is further discussed in the reflection on the quality of studies.

Some generational differences were reported. Zasiiekina et al. (2021) noted that the third generation showed more signs of trauma integration, compared to the second one, given the differences in the interviews – more words used, more details described, higher coherence of their accounts. The authors suggested that with every generation the communication may become freer. They also noticed that the third generation showed more preparedness to understand and create family narratives, as well as more motivation to pass these stories forward, compared to the second generation.

5.3 Resilience

5.3.1 Soviet Regime

Resilience was associated with a sense of identity (Baker & Gippenreiter, 1994; Javakhishvili, 2018; Vaskelienė et al., 2011). Baker and Gippenreiter (1994) found that the third generation who was engaged in researching their family's genocide history, tended to have higher levels of resilience. Vaskelienė et al. (2011) concluded that the coping strategies transmitted to the second generation included resilience, strength, a sense of meaning in their lives, pride in the parents and respect for them, patriotism, and even a sense of superiority since they were the ones knowing the truth shared by their families. Similarly,

Javakhishvili (2018) framed the resilience found among the third generation as a force impacting their patriotic values, empathetic personality, and fighting spirit.

Resilience was higher in families affected by deportations, imprisonment and killings (Kazlauskas & Želvienė, 2016; Mažulytė-Rašytinė, 2017). Kazlauskas and Želvienė (2016) reported that the well-being of the families with the oppressive background was found to be higher than in the families without it. Interestingly, the experience of lifetime traumatic events was not associated with lower well-being. According to the authors, it suggests that the oppressive experiences may facilitate the transmission of resilience and even well-being for the future generations, which may count as a protective mechanism against traumatic events in the lives of the offspring. Mažulytė-Rašytinė (2017) identified that the second and third generation participants from the victim families had higher well-being, higher resilience, as well as more optimism and hope, compared to the families without exposure to direct Soviet oppression.

One study explicitly addressed the transmission of resilience from the first to the second generation, suggesting that parental resilience is associated with child resilience. Namely, they found a correlation between the sense of coherence in the parents and offspring of the oppressed families (Kazlauskas et al., 2017).

5.3.2 Nazi Regime

In the Holocaust studies, resilience and ways of coping were portrayed both as behaviours and personality traits (Braga et al., 2012; Giladi & Bell, 2012; Shrira et al., 2011). Braga et al. (2012) found the transmitted acts of resilience such as visiting locations connected to family trauma, expression through art, joining communities, and activism. Giladi and Bell (2012) reported the presence of resilience in the examples of focusing on high achievement, choosing empathetic careers, and sharing the legacy of Holocaust. Shrira et al. (2011) concluded that the offspring of Holocaust survivors had more optimism, hope, and satisfaction with life compared to the non-Holocaust group. The authors also found that resilience is observed more in families with affectionate and open communication, as described in the previous section (Braga et al, 2012).

On a different note, Kidron et al. (2019) found that the offspring of Holocaust survivors see the transmitted resilience and vulnerability as interlinked rather than distinct concepts, interacting and reinforcing each other. They suggested the concept of resilient vulnerability to explain their results.

5.4 Additional Findings

While the studies in this review were selected to address the research questions related to the transmission of trauma through family communication, attachment styles, parenting

approaches, as well as transmission of resilience, these studies provided additional findings that may enrich the understanding of the topic. In this section, the additional findings, that were consistently occurring in the reviewed studies, will be presented.

5.4.1 Societal

5.4.1.1 Soviet Regime. On the societal level, mistrust of other people was transmitted through generations (Baker & Gippenreiter, 1994; Bezo & Maggi, 2015; Javakhishvili, 2018). Even relatives would often refrain from communicating with the second generation of oppressed families out of fear – the third generation claimed that because of the hostility from the state and rejection from the community, they learned to mistrust others (Javakhishvili, 2018). Both the second and the third generations talked about fear and mistrust of other people as a result of Holodomor, leading to isolation from others in society (Bezo & Maggi, 2015).

Bezo and Maggi (2015) also found the transmitted sense of indifference towards other people among second and third generation participants, that arose as a need for self-preservation during Holodomor, encouraging the focus on survival of the family and ignoring the struggle of others. Participants claimed that in the present-day Ukraine society, people are less generous towards each other or concerned with helping each other. They attributed this to learning and trauma transmission through the social environment (Bezo & Maggi, 2015).

The authors also reported on lost opportunities (Baker & Gippenreiter, 1994; Javakhishvili, 2018). The third generation in Russia talked about jobs that they would not be admitted to despite qualifications, because they were the offspring of the oppression victims (Baker & Gippenreiter, 1994). Similarly, the second generation in Georgia experienced hostility resulting in inability to get a job, pursue medical studies, obtain music education, and go abroad (Javakhishvili, 2018).

5.4.1.2 Nazi Regime. Among the Holocaust studies, only one study found the participants reporting mistrust. The second generation described being raised with reminders not to connect with people, and not to fall in love. They thought they may have passed this sentiment to their daughters – the third generation (Zasiekina et al., 2021).

5.4.2 Individual

5.4.2.1 Soviet Regime. Both the second and the third generations reported elements of passivity and helplessness (Baker & Gippenreiter, 1994; Bezo & Maggi, 2015; Javakhishvili, 2018). The third generation in the Russian sample stated that they struggle with taking initiative (Baker & Gippenreiter, 1994). In the Georgian sample, the third generation tried to stay invisible and avoid people, with their second-generation parents

describing this tendency as well, explaining it as an attempt to stay safe and unseen, since their own parents were anxious about their children being noticed by the regime and affected by oppressions (Javakhishvili, 2018). In the Ukrainian sample, both the second and the third generations talked about the fear to take action that was transmitted from their parents, leading to what they described as slave mentality. It was related to inability to actively make decisions in the spheres of employment and personal life, leading to passivity and low self-esteem (Bezo & Maggi, 2015).

5.4.2.2 Nazi Regime. No Holocaust studies discussed a lack of initiative or attempt to stay unseen. One study addressed low self-worth (Gangi et al., 2009).

5.5. Analytical themes

The results of the studies reveal three key analytical themes, that can be unified into one suggested mechanism. One of the most prominent themes that emerged was open family communication leading to resilience patterns. It was related to the mechanisms of strengthened identity and emotional processing, such as using expressions of humour or even sadness when talking about family trauma. Another analytical theme addressed the link between fragmented, absent, or overly detailed communication and more traumatic symptoms. Finally, a theme was identified around family communication type correlating with parenting approaches, with a lack of communication being associated with avoidance of traumatic topics, leading to parentification and numbness.

Taken together, multiple codes and themes suggest a pattern showing that the family atmosphere of anxiety and fear affects parenting approaches, communication, and attachment styles. Negative mental health symptoms such as anxiety, sadness and fear may lead to more overprotective or avoidant parenting approaches, at points leading to insecure attachment, which results in more fractured and less open family communication, and which may then influence the transmission of such attributes and processes to the next generation.

5.6 Critical Evaluation of the Quality of Studies Presented

Nineteen out of 23 studies were peer-reviewed. Out of the remaining four, two studies were published as doctoral dissertations and two studies as chapters. The analysis of the research journals in which the studies were published, indicated that the journals follow rigorous peer review policies. All of them described the review process as anonymous or blinded, and eight of them characterised it as double blinded or double masked. Given the limited number of studies on the topic, especially the studies on the Soviet regime, it was important to include all academic data available, while carefully evaluating the conclusions that it presents. Therefore, while not all the studies were peer-reviewed, the ones that were,

came from journals with robust review processes, and the ones that were not, were checked by the authors of the books in which the research chapters got published and by the doctoral dissertation supervisors. The findings of non-peer-reviewed studies were consistent with the rest of the studies.

Eight studies had control groups. Since half of the studies had qualitative elements, a lack of control groups may be understood due to the exploratory nature of qualitative research goals. In addition, finding relevant comparison groups in this research field may be difficult, as historical trauma affects entire populations. However, a lack of comparison, especially coupled with non-random sampling, may make the conclusions less robust and thus, less generalisable and less replicable.

Only three studies used random samples. The remaining ones relied on recruiting via networks and convenience samples – obtaining the participant contacts from governmental data registries (such as Israeli Ministry of the Interior), or nongovernmental organisations related to traumatic experiences (such as Lithuanian Genocide and Resistance Research Center, Jewish Community of Rome and Milan, Brazilian Jewish Institution, Memorial organisation dedicated to Stalin's Purge victims). In addition, the nature of research limits the participant characteristics: research that involved the elderly first generation participants, tended to over-represent women, as women tend to live longer than men (World Health Organisation, 2018). Only the participants that were willing to be a part of the research were included, which means that survivors of more extreme experiences and their families may not have been represented, as recalling these experiences in the context of research may have been too painful. While a lack of random sampling may seem problematic, the research on historical intergenerational trauma requires participants with rather specific experiences, and while the results may not be fully representable of the wider society, they still offer insight into the process of trauma transmission in the researched communities.

Two studies had limitations in operationalising the researched variables. One study measured sense of coherence while using the results for conclusions on resilience, without using scales measuring resilience (Kazlauskas et al., 2017). Another study assessed trauma transmission through response latency in a Stroop test. While the authors indicated that no other study has used this procedure before to assess trauma transmission, they defined trauma transmission as response latency in this test, and when the hypothesis was not supported, they concluded that the trauma transmission to the third generation may not occur (Kassai & Motta, 2006). Having said that, both operationalisation options can be argued for, nonetheless, construct validity of these studies may be affected. While Kazlauskas et al. (2017) mentioned this operationalisation choice as a potential limitation,

Kassai and Motta (2006) did not acknowledge downsides of this procedure in measuring trauma transmission.

Twelve studies in this review used quantitative measurements - only, or in addition to qualitative analysis of the interviews. Even when quantitative scales were used, most of them relied on self-report, which might have been problematic in the cases where participants had to recall their experiences from many years ago (such as stories from their childhood), when they had to describe vulnerable experiences of their own (such as evaluating their well-being), or when they had to make judgements that may be hard to observe from the first person (such as evaluating if their grandparents experiences had influence on their lives). The qualitative study results may not be generalisable. However, the quantitative findings tended to be consistent with qualitative ones, offering both generalisable insight and deeper understanding behind the quantitative findings.

Two studies did not specify if the participants belonged to the second or third generation. In one case, it was stated that all participants were from the second or third generation. In another study, it was mentioned that the participants are family members of the victims. While this lack of specificity did not seem to significantly affect the study as the results of these studies were largely consistent with the rest of them in the review, knowing which generations specifically were studied would have allowed for a more insightful analysis.

One study had only six participants – since it had conclusions that were slightly different to the others, these conclusions may need to be approached cautiously (Cohn & Morrison, 2018).

Finally, three studies did not include any limitations.

There are a lot of signs of quality research in this sample. Three studies implemented control for immigration effects, which is especially relevant to the Nazi genocide sample as it includes many people who moved to Israel, so it is important to understand if their struggles can be partially explained by immigration. Secondly, three studies controlled for the degree of trauma transmission when only one of the parents had family trauma history, compared to both parents coming from trauma-affected families. Thirdly, six studies controlled for traumatic experiences in participants' lives, to understand if there are any other variables that may have influenced their current state, other than the family trauma transmission.

5.7 Contribution to the Research Field

The finding that historical trauma in the Soviet and Nazi genocide samples was related to insecure attachment types, is consistent with the wider trauma research field. In a study on Armenian genocide, Ghrjyan (2023) found that insecure attachment correlated with the

transmission of intergenerational trauma. A systematic review on refugee trauma found that parental traumatic experiences affected their children through insecure attachment (Flanagan et al., 2020). Consistent with these results was the finding that adult children of Holocaust survivors showed lower capacity for emotional intimacy in their romantic relationships, while being more emotionally connected to their parents than the comparison group (Mazor & Tal, 1996). This is supported by Family Systems theory, implying a struggle for differentiation, as well as displaying elements of anxious attachment. One Holocaust study in the sample did not find any connection between attachment styles and the historical trauma, which can be related to studies in the literature that did not find consequences of historical trauma to second or third generations (Sagi-Schwartz et al., 2008; Van IJzendoorn et al., 2003). The authors suggested that a lack of secondary or tertiary traumatising could be explained by the presence of resilience.

Communication was another way of trauma transmission in the Soviet and Nazi genocide samples: open communication more often correlated with better social and psychological functioning, and absent or fragmented communication was linked to more traumatic transmission. In a study on Apartheid, the second generation reported a lack of communication in the family, as well as a lack of societal conversation about the trauma (Hoosain, 2013). A study on Rwandan genocide reported disturbed family communication, such as silence out of fear of talking about the traumatic events, as well as due to parentification (Ingabire et al., 2022). These findings also contribute to the Family Systems theory, showing how traumatic parental experiences may lead to parent-child role reversal, resulting in avoidance of communication out of mutual protection. Importantly, parent-child role reversal can be linked to insecure attachment, and while not many studies in this sample focused on attachment styles, one found the connection between insecure attachment and parentification as well, consistent with wider literature (Baggett et al., 2015; Engelhardt, 2012). Another element of Family Systems theory was supported by the finding that differentiation of self and open communication were linked to lower traumatic stress. Other studies in the field provided similar findings on differentiation of self, showing that lower differentiation of self of the offspring can be related to higher post-traumatic symptoms in ex-prisoners of war and their children (Nicolai et al., 2017). The authors explained this effect through children's inability to develop and protect their individuality due to the family environment influenced by anxiety, overprotection and fear stemming from parental trauma.

The research on intergenerationally transmitted resilience within the field of trauma, and especially historical trauma, is relatively new. In this study, resilience was often transmitted through familial and cultural identities embedded in family communication, consistent with Family Systems theory, suggesting that family members benefit from relying

on each other, and that family values such as shared identity correspond with presence of resilience (Bowen, 1978). Other studies on genocides offer comparable findings. A study on Cambodian genocide found open and less hierarchical parental communication to be related to resilience transmission (Mak et al., 2021). Some studies in the sample discovered not only resilience, but higher levels of well-being when compared to the control group, implying post-traumatic growth. The connection between more open communication within family and higher levels of well-being is further evidenced by a link between storytelling and post-traumatic growth in the context of race-based historical trauma, as well as the genocide in Rwanda (Chin et al., 2023; Grayson, 2018). According to Cozolino (2016), storytelling is hardwired in human beings, and therefore, family stories become common transmission pathways.

This review has found the pattern of intergenerationally transmitted mistrust and helplessness, especially in the Soviet genocide sample. While not widely researched in the context of intergenerational historical trauma, mistrust has been noticed in communities of indigenous people in Canada affected by genocidal policies, as well as in the genocide-affected Rwanda (Ingelaere & Verpoorten, 2020; Leckey et al., 2022; Manirakiza, 2018). More generally, a sense of helplessness is shown to be associated with traumatic experiences (Herman, 1992).

6. Discussion

6.1 Addressing the Research Questions

6.1.1 Attachment Styles and Parenting Approaches

Elements of insecure attachment were found to be transmitted to second and third generations in both samples, with two cases of ambivalent attachment, a case of disorganised attachment and a study describing insecure attachment without specifying its type. While one study focused on attachment found no evidence for insecure attachment transmission, the presence of the other studies suggests that insecure, and especially ambivalent, attachment might be present in the offspring of genocide survivors. Parental overprotection and parent-child role reversal were found to be transmitted intergenerationally as well. In addition, parenting styles were found to be transmitted from the first to the second generation. The results often describing a family atmosphere of fear and anxiety support this conclusion.

6.1.2 Family Communication

Trauma was transmitted through family communication in three key ways. Firstly, a lack of communication or fragmented communication was associated with more traumatic effects

getting transmitted, some studies finding that overly detailed communication had similar effects. Secondly, open and affective communication was linked to higher resilience and well-being transmitted – as well as stronger identity. Thirdly, non-verbal communication was found to transmit the traumatic effects without explicitly talking about them, but only in one case.

6.1.3 Resilience

Resilience was transmitted through open family communication, the sense of family and community identity, as well as behaviours such as activism or visiting meaningful sites. The offspring from families affected by trauma reported higher well-being and optimism in some studies, especially in the Soviet regime sample. In some of them, the absence of traumatic effects was explained through the presence of resilience. In addition, having one parent not affected by genocides could count as a protective factor. One study suggested that resilience is non-distinct from vulnerability, defining resilient vulnerability as a concept present in trauma transmission.

6.1.4 Differences in Samples

The trauma transmission mechanisms discussed in the studies of Soviet and Nazi genocides were remarkably similar and overlapping. There were two key differences between the samples. Firstly, on top of the emotional silence induced by the traumatic events, there was a political silence present in the Soviet genocide studies, even when the genocidal actions such as Holodomor or deportations to Siberia were over. A lack of communication about the family trauma was also more often mentioned in the Soviet regime sample, with all but one of them touching on it. Secondly, helplessness and a lack of initiative were often mentioned in the Soviet genocide studies, while they were never mentioned in the Nazi genocide, which some of the authors explained through the fact that Soviet committed genocides are rarely known or acknowledged.

6.1.5 Generation effects

While the differences between the second and the third generations were not a part of the research questions, some generational observations contribute to the understanding of the transmission addressed in the research questions. Overall, most of the results applied both to the transmission to the second and to the third generations. However, in some studies the third generation had reduced traumatic reactions, compared to the second generation. They showed milder behavioural reactions and provided more cohesive responses, using more words when speaking about the historical trauma and sharing more details than the second generation. In addition, the third generation more than the second tended to notice positive outcomes related to the historical trauma, such as family resilience. Some of the authors

explain this effect as parents consciously trying to raise their children differently to prevent the transmission of traumatic symptoms that they inherited themselves.

6.2 Summary of Results

To sum up, the results of this literature review show that there is evidence for family communication as a transmission pathway in intergenerational trauma, with open communication being more associated with transmission of resilience, and absent communication associated with symptoms of PTSD, anxiety, sadness. Traumatic experiences were also found to be transmitted through insecure attachment styles and controlling or avoidant parental approaches. Some families affected by genocides showed only resilience with no traumatic outcomes. The outcomes in Nazi and Soviet genocide samples were comparable, with the variable of mistrust and helplessness featuring mostly in the families affected by the Soviet regime. The limitations of the study and the nuance with which the data should be interpreted will be discussed up next.

6.3 Limitations

6.3.1 Critical Reflection on Research Strategy

While the inclusion criteria accounted for only English language studies, the exception was made for one Lithuanian language study due to the author's native proficiency in it. One study was excluded due to language, when no translated version was found. This may introduce a bias into the sample, however, the Lithuanian study that was accepted showed similar patterns to other studies and did not skew the results. Given how limited the current research field is, it was important to use all the data available to present the research that is as conclusive and comprehensive as possible.

Some studies that were selected were not accessible – the full versions of the articles were not available to the author. Effort was made to find the email addresses of the authors and to ask for a copy of the articles. Four authors agreed to share their articles, which enabled the analysis of their studies. No email address was found for two articles, which deprived this review from a more comprehensive view. The abstracts of the missing articles suggested that their data was largely in agreement with the studies analysed in this review.

While established scientific research databases PsycNet, DOAJ and PubMed were utilised in the search, some databases like ScienceGov ended up not being used in the process after testing the search strings on them and finding that they returned insufficient results. When conducting the literature search on the databases, Boolean operators were not used, because after initial string testing, they did not return relevant results. However, the search and analysis processes were clearly documented, so that other researchers can

replicate them. Inclusion criteria was chosen to lean towards capturing more studies, in order not to miss limited data, and studies were sifted through manually to find articles relevant to the research questions. Every study found was documented with a noted reason for exclusion, to account for duplicates and to lead the process with transparency. The thematic analysis of the studies was described through codes and themes, to share visibility on the process.

Although Nazi genocide includes more atrocities than Holocaust, most of the literature found was focused exclusively on Holocaust, which may not reveal the full picture of the traumatic impact by the regime. More search strings might need to be tested to capture the non-Holocaust Nazi impact on trauma transmission. In addition, more research in the field is needed.

On a positive note, while studies on the Soviet regime are extremely limited, the selected search strategy was successful in producing all the empirical studies that are currently available and that concern the intergenerational trauma transmission, to the best of the author's knowledge. To check the sensitivity of the search procedure, a comprehensive Google Scholar search was conducted to cross-reference the included papers and to make sure that there are no additional studies in this field missing from the sample of this review. It was concluded that all the studies that address the research question and are available on Google Scholar were detected on the academic databases used in the search procedure.

6.3.2 Critical Reflection on the Master's Thesis

There were multiple papers by the same authors in this review. While it may introduce a bias in the sample, it reflects how limited the research in the field is for now. Since their research questions did not completely overlap, these research papers were kept to provide a more detailed view of the literature.

The comparison groups in the studies varied - while in some studies they consisted of participants who have never experienced anything similar to a genocide, other samples, especially the ones focusing on the Soviet regime, had the comparison samples of people who have lived under the Soviet regime, albeit not directly affected by genocidal actions. As a result, in these cases the differences between the groups may be less established.

Although the conclusions of the studies were quite consistent, each research question of the review had a varying number of studies addressing it, in the varying levels of depth. Family communication as a trauma transmission pathway was addressed by the most research papers, while attachment transmission was covered less frequently. Having said that, the research questions were addressed with a mixture of qualitative and quantitative studies for each question, providing both potential for generalisable data and insight behind

the pattern. No systematic differences were noticed between outcomes of quantitative and qualitative studies for the same research questions, suggesting that the qualitative studies, although not generalisable, are largely consistent with quantitative data.

The author of this review is Lithuanian, whose great grandparent was deported to Siberia by the Soviet regime. As a result, this background may introduce a bias in this study. To prevent it, the author followed the scientific principles to document an impartial process and unbiased results. For example, the use of integrative methodology and thematic analysis allowed for a comprehensive synthesis of different studies to go beyond descriptive results and understand the interactions among the studies, the different samples, generations and methodological approaches.

While the trauma in both samples fell under comparable definitions of genocide, the research was conducted in different countries, under different political and cultural settings. It is likely that trauma exposure was different in different families and communities, and while quantitative studies may attempt to account for it through random sampling, the qualitative studies that are abundant in this research may not be fully representative and therefore may not reflect on entire populations.

The genocidal status of Stalin's crimes and ethnic cleansing of Georgians, Lithuanians, Ukrainians, and other occupied nations is sometimes questioned, but according to the documentation cited in Introduction, these crimes of Holodomor, Stalin's Purge and mass deportations to Siberia can be classified as genocides and thus compared to Nazi Holocaust. Importantly, the similarity of the findings between the two samples supports this classification.

6.4 Implications and Practical Recommendations

These findings have implications for individual and societal settings, leading to practical recommendations.

On the individual level, these findings have implications for the mental health professionals working with clients who may experience intergenerational trauma. On the one hand, it is important to acknowledge the promising findings of resilience transmitted intergenerationally, and therefore, not to victimise the patients, and rather help them uncover their own coping resources and skills. On the other hand, many significant vulnerabilities can be transmitted as well, and these findings may help clinical psychologists to provide their patients with deeper understanding of their family histories and personal experiences. The findings imply that the most effective interventions may relate to open and empathetic communication within the family. This type of communication is associated with an ability to process trauma, and therefore to move towards post-traumatic growth. Therefore, focusing

on communication within family would be recommended for mental health professionals working with the patients that may have the family history of intergenerational historical trauma.

On the societal level, these findings imply that the traumatic consequences under both Nazi and Soviet regimes were comparable, and that more research on the psychological impact of Soviet regime is needed not only to close the empirical gap, but also to provide an opportunity for the post-Soviet communities to understand their and their family's experience, to see it internationally acknowledged, and to process it communally. A lack of justice and acknowledgement may prevent trauma processing and explain the helplessness expressed by the families affected by these genocides (Bezo, 2017; Heart & DeBruyn, 1998; Javakhishvili, 2018). Practical societal campaigns and educational policies are needed to help the communities break the cycle of trauma by encouraging trust, emotional communication and institutional changes (Isobel et al., 2019). Support groups and similar communal constructs can be recommended for storytelling, processing traumatic events, and leaning into the resilience factors: discussing shared identity, pride of ancestors, strength that can be derived from the family stories (Friskie, 2020).

6.5 Future Research Questions

Studies discussed in this review largely relied on self-report by the participants. Future research should focus on more objective assessments, including biological measurements such as cortisol levels, amygdala activity, structured observation of attachment styles, as well as analysis of organic family communication, focusing on emotions and beliefs shared. Artificial Intelligence can now diagnose depression and anxiety by analysing words and their emotional quality, so in the future this technology could be tested on the cases of intergenerational trauma, since the symptoms tend to be deeply ingrained and normalised, so self-reported experiences may not be accurate (Lin et al., 2022). Having said that, intergenerational trauma is a complex phenomenon, and subjective, qualitative accounts will stay essential to understanding people's experiences behind the quantitative metrics. Future research could focus on exploring to what extent biological trauma transmission markers and psychological self-report scales correlate.

Most of the studies related to Soviet genocide were conducted in Lithuania, with two studies set in Ukraine, one in Russia and one in Georgia. Studies in different countries affected by this regime are needed to understand to what degree the findings can be generalised. In addition, studies analysing people who emigrated abroad might help to understand to what extent trauma is transmitted purely through the family environment, and to what extent the societal environment contributes to it.

As the findings on the value of open communication were so pronounced, it would be useful to conduct research to see if open family communication may work as an intervention, even if survivors' offspring were raised in the context of absent communication about the traumatic experiences. In addition, different types of communication contexts could be researched, trying to understand if communication about the traumatic experiences within the community can be effective when it happens outside of the family unit, and how it may affect the trauma transmission to the future generations.

Since studies found different strengths and vulnerabilities that were transmitted due to intergenerational trauma, as well as different degrees of transmission, future research may focus on identifying what makes certain individuals and families more vulnerable, and more resilient. The findings on resilience in the context of intergenerational trauma is emerging and may offer an empowering rather than a victimising perspective, therefore, more research is needed to understand the variables relevant to the transmission of resilience in traumatic contexts. Finally, since this is a new field and the studies are few, more replications are needed.

6.6. Conclusion

This integrative literature review analysed the transmission of historical intergenerational trauma and used thematic analysis to discover that family communication is one of the most prominent ways of passing trauma from one generation to the next, with absent communication often associated with more trauma transmission, and more open communication associated with transmission of resilience. The insecure attachment styles were also found to be transmitted intergenerationally, often due to the emotional effects of the trauma, such as fear, anxiety, sadness leading to parental overprotection or avoidance, parent-child role reversal and less supportive parental styles. However, half of the studies were qualitative and hence offered limited generalisability. In addition, a limited number of studies did not find evidence for trauma transmission – in some of those cases, it was explained by the transmission of resilience. More research is needed to understand the transmission of resilience and the circumstances that facilitate it. In addition, future studies could cover more cultural contexts: while Soviet-committed genocides affected over 15 countries for over 60 years, only eight relevant studies from four countries were found (Fischer, 1994; Kenez, 2016). The results of the review were similar across both Soviet and Nazi genocide samples, therefore, the transmission of the historical intergenerational trauma in these samples may be seen as similar, and more research is needed to examine it better – both to provide more quantitative insight, and to replicate the findings.

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Word Count

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